

TYPES OF PATTERNS AND BASIC LEGISLATION OF THE COMPOSITION OF PATTERNS

Rakhmatova Laylo Ibodullaevna

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute
2nd course Master's degree
+99893 433 70 32

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the types of patterns, what colors and signs mean and the composition of the pattern

Patterns will have a unique style, technology and meaning that will not decorate the piece, wall or anywhere. What is the pattern itself? What are its types? What do you understand when you say Pattern Language?

Pattern-Arabic image, means a flower. a bird is an ornament formed by the repetition of an animal, a plant, a geometrical and other elements in a certain order.

Crafts, jewelry, carpet weaving, wood carving and wood carving are processed in patterns in different ways. For example: engrave, draw, pinned with a tattoo using a stitch and knit in other ways.

According to the content of the patterns used in the carving of Ganch - it is divided into vegetative, geometrical, floral girix, symbolic and other species. The plant-like patterns are made from the reproduction of leaves, bandages, trees, shrubs, buds and other things in nature on the basis of certain

regularities of the stylized form obtained by carvings. One of the types of geometrical patterns is girix, which means tangled, knot. Trench pattern is a type of complex pattern. The geometrical pattern is one of the Marrakech patterns and consists of a rectangle, a triangle, a circle and a polygon with arcs. The tail is divided into girix, which consists of a straight line, a curved line and a mixed line. The geometrical pattern consists of continuous rapporteurs, each rapport will have its own structure. In Europe it is referred to as arabesque.

Floral girix consists of elements of vegetation and geometrical patterns. Its elements include the above listed geometrical and vegetative patterns.

And the symbolic patterns are made up of elements of the pattern, which are depicted by stylizing pigeons, Lions, Pisces, state emblem and others.

While our ancestors decorated their ancient monuments with elegant

ornaments, as well as enjoying them, they sang through them their dreams, correspondences, wishes. Our illustrious ancestors enriched their minds with amazing figurines by studying the human mind very deeply and in all directions. Those in the House who are patterned to be in a calm, spiritual tranquility, wise grandfathers of longevity have hooks based on centuries-old experiences of life.

Our old masters say that in ancient times the art of embroidery was so developed that they could speak with each other in a consonant sound through their drawing or painted patterns. In order to know the language of the art of embroidery, it is necessary to know the symbolic alphabet of the elements and colors of the pattern.

Famous scientists, poets and illustrators of the world such as Amur Temur, Alisher Navoi, Abu Raykhon Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Al-Khwarizmi, Nizami Ganjavi, Nasir Khisrav, Kamoliddin Bekhzad, Mauni, Firsiysi, Omar Khayyam, Babur have decorated their buildings with the patterns to the beautiful landscapes, attracting the imagination of people. Those who encouraged people to be close friends, brothers with beauty.

Let's take a look at the old city center of Samarkand, the Sherdor Madrasah, which is pouring a basket in Registan. Its roofs, rich domes and beautiful minarets, colorful glazed mosaics and elegant, luxurious silent coating fascinates the person.

This Madrasah, like other architectural monuments, has its own meaning and history. During the reign of Muhammad Imamkulkhan, one of the Ashtar Khans in Bukhara, the Khan's most reliable and close person, that is, after the enrichment of the governor of Samarkand- Yalangtashbiy

Bahadir, finally, built the Sherdor Madrasah, which was a miracle of its time in 1619-1636, in front of Mirzo Ulugbek madrasah in Samarkand.

This magnificent building will add glamour to the city's splendour and will be worthy of the applause of all poets, scholars, scientists the people of the city, barefoot architect Abdu Jabbar put before him the task of conveying to the people through ornaments that he would not be able to stay from his great ancestors from one thing to another. The famous architect, who possessed the key to art, was able to convey his philosophical thought to the people with the language of the pattern in a consonant voice. The main facade of the Sherdor Madrasah is of attractive appearance, its façade is decorated with symbolic patterns that make it proportional (symmetrical), and the reddish gilded Tiger Lions chase and chase the thin oxen, and the man who is behind them is imbued with an image of the sun, and the gilded one.

Islimiy nakshu Nigari from their surroundings. The image depicts an agile, strong, invincible lion, symbolically depicted as symbolizing its weakness, which is signaled barefoot happiness. And the sun was taken as a symbol of that period and life. The tenderness of the universe and peace through dark colored mosaics reflected Boku Boston, nature through vegetative patterns.

What is the symbol in the genitive case? - It is derived from the Arabic word "point out", by nature, to portray the joy and anxiety of life through elements of patterns, vivid lines, colors of friends and enemies, good and evil.

Now we will get acquainted with the Uzbek national Pattern Language alphabet. They are an expression from the following:

Symbolic meanings of geometric pattern elements:

An equilateral triangle is a standing position in which the beginning of life is the same, and the opposite standing position denotes the end of life.

An equilateral triangle is a holistic piece, a parting.

Square-four sides of the world, the palace of heaven, the child of the sun, eternity, lightness, self-sufficiency.

A straight rectangle is a trust.

Rhombus is a woman, that is, a symbol of Mother Earth, serfdom. A circle is a symbol of happiness, the sun, slipping people from evil intentions. Five-pointed path is a shortcut to life, a five-day world. Half a circle - happiness.

Half Moon-the expression of the religion of Islam. A symbol of Islam.

Right swastika-eternal movement, growth, ascent.

Left swastika-reverse movement, straining. The sun is a symbol of life.

Cloud fire is a symbol of mold.

Symbolic meanings of elements of muslim pattern:

Almond-Iqbal of happiness. Awakening of leaves and leaves. Pepper is a symbol of various evils and evil eye-catching.

Barberry blossom- (Gulsafsar) - peace and longevity.

Pomegranate-goodness, satiety, fullness.

Aygul is a symbol of happiness.

Curly-a symbol of full hair, wealth.

Apples are a symbol of love.

Rod-wealth and prosperity.

Leaf-satiety, Spring Awakening, New day.

Harmel is a symbol of evil eye.

Roses are a symbol of beauty.

Symbolic meanings of birds and animals:

A lion is a symbol of courage and courage, strength.

Fox-cunning.

Ant-a symbol of wisdom, chastity.

Nightingale-loyalty.

Humo is a bird that brings happiness.

Owl-misfortune.

Pisces is a symbol of sympathy.

Mouse-a symbol of the reproduction of domestic animals.

Goat-courage, courage.

White dove-peace.

Gazelle- beauty, tenderness.

Symbolic meanings of colours:

Green colour is a symbol of Mother Nature.

Blue colour is the blue sky.

Red colour- victory, joy.

Yellow colour is an inevitability.

Black colour-mourning.

Yellow flower-parting.

Bluish-high faith.

White colour-freshness, light.

Composition.

Artistic finishing works, like all types of Fine Arts, are carried out in the case when both come from the General Laws of composition. Therefore, all these works require sufficient knowledge and skills from the decorative artist, while constantly focusing on the issues of composition.

In the work of artistic decoration, there are mainly three types of composition: flat, oblique, having width and depth. All this will have some common qualities and signs in the implementation of this or that idea.

Frontal composition-this means the organization of a frontal image according to two coordinates. A characteristic feature of the Frontal composition is the restriction of the use of oblique elements in it and, at the

same time, the possibility of increasing its dimensions. Therefore, if some relief images (for example: cuttings, wood pulp ganch carvings and hackos) are seen on the basis of the laws of plasticity, then both are of the type of flat surface compositions. Most of the decorative works in educational institutions, for example, sight guns, wall papers, thematic posters, invitations, greeting cards, thematic albums and papers, are performed on the basis of frontal composition. The construction of the composition depends on the content of the concentration of the function of a particular object, on the intended purpose. The main points of the composition are the following: horizontal composition – this is where the elements of the composition are placed on the horizontal surface. For example: a field, a panorama of the city, etc.

Vertical composition is an active, dynamic composition, upward growth, dressing the flight imagination, the details of which are located mainly on the steep line.

Diagonal composition-its construction is based on dynamic and rigid schemes.

1. Triangular or pyramidal composition – this is based on a stable, calm state. The lower part of the surface of the photo is the basis of the pyramid. One of the features of the frontal compositions in the art of artistic decoration is their execution in the style of a thin surface. Frontal composition from other types of compositions, it differs in that it gives distance and width. The composition with volume comes in a three-dimensional form, designed for perception from different points of view. In accordance with the content and function of the works, it can become a feature of the composition. The composition, by its properties, ultimately

serves as the basis for ensuring the high artistic merit of the work of artistic decoration. In the harmonic integrity of the compositions, the colors acquire great significance in both specifically. Especially it is necessary to take seriously the composition harmony in the showcases of Mosaic panno, where the color is the main place. Only then will the color unit of the work become one of the main factors affecting aesthetics. Unreasonable deviations from the laws of composition usually decrease the content of works of artistic finishing, aesthetic Moss Ham. If the elements of the composition are located relative to each other on the sides, then they will be in the balance of the composition. One of the main issues in the composition is the combination. By changing the location of one and several elements on the basis of the combination, a new expressive variant of the composition is prepared. Both dynamic and static compositions have their own laws. Between these it is necessary to avoid the emergence of a dependent meaning, that is, to achieve a logical harmony of the main and secondary elements. Knowing the laws of rhythm impressive composition will greatly help to correctly choose the character of the rhythmic appearance in the lap.

In conclusion, we can say that one of the important conditions in ensuring the effectiveness of research carried out in the edagogic direction is the development of a special methodology. As a result of the organization of experimental and test works on the basis of a special methodology, their effectiveness was not only ensured, but also laid the groundwork for the

successful conduct of the study. We came to the following conclusions.

1. Special attention is paid to the identification of talented students in higher education practice, determination of measures for effective use of opportunities of educational work and spiritual and educational activities.

2. Development of ability of students on the basis of Decision-Making of higher education and strong cooperation between family, neighborhood and the general public.

3. At the higher education level – the establishment of the club named "ididorli student".

4. To determine the general characteristics of children.

5. The results of the diagnosis conducted by the teachers of Science, the leaders of the circle, the parents IQT data on the areas of competence should be formalized in the form of tables;

6. IQT planning of educational work with the opportunity to demonstrate the skills of senior students.

Relying on these conclusions, it is possible to give the following recommendations on the development of pedagogical and psychological effects of working with senior students in higher educational institutions:

-Development of different programs of working with children in higher educational institutions;

-To provide separate complex teaching assignments for senior students in the content of textbooks and manuals and lesson developments of the new generation created in the process of Higher Education;
-to carry out separate research works for each class on creative researchers, scientific researchers, culture and sports, as well as on the directions of programmers in the section of subjects developed as a national educational initiative;

-development of educational programs on the work of teachers with children with disabilities in the process of professional development and retraining of personnel;

- IQT create electronic programs and websites for working with senior students.

- enrichment with new psychological techniques that identify ADHD;

- cooperation of science teachers and parents in the development of leadership students;

- to identify and make recommendations on students' ability, Ability, and ability to orientate in their professional career from the very first age;

- Organization of various circles taking into account the interests of students;

- to determine the direction of providing deepened knowledge based on the requirements and needs of the educational institution;

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